

Dynamic Resource Allocation for Media Streaming in Cloud Storage

¹Deepashree H. L

Assistant Professor,

Department of Computer Science and Engineering
PES University, RR Campus

Abstract:- Media streaming applications have recently been envisioned to a large number of users in the Internet. This huge demand creates a burden on centralized data centers at media content and has turned out to a research area. The problem becomes more critical with the increasing demand for higher bit rates required for the growing number of higher-definition video quality desired by consumers. Most of the existing cloud providers employ a pricing model for the reserved resources that is based on non-linear time-discount tariffs. Such a pricing scheme offers discount rates depending non-linearly on the period of time during which the resources are reserved in the cloud. This can be resolved by Prediction-Based Resource Allocation algorithm. The proposed system is an android application based, as smart phones are more in use.

Keywords: Video; Streaming; Media; Resource; Prediction-Based.

I. INTRODUCTION

Media streaming have recently pulled a countless people on network. Streaming media is multimedia that is perpetually gotten by, showed to an end-customer while being passed by a supplier. The verb "to stream" is the methodology of conveying media. A customer media player can start to play the information, before the whole record has been transmitted. Recognizing conveyance procedure from the media appropriated applies especially to information transfers systems, as a huge part of the conveyance frameworks are either intrinsically streaming (TV) or intrinsically non-streaming (Books). The expression "streaming media" can apply to media other than video and sound, for example, real-time text, which is viewed as "streaming content". The key particular issues related to streaming were as one is Having sufficient CPU power and transport transfer speed to bolster the required information rates

Another one is Making low-inactivity interfere with ways in the working framework to avert cradle under run. Streaming media is logically being consolidated with use of internet systems administration. For instance, YouTube support social participation in webcasts through components, for occurrence, live visit, online studies, and so forth. Besides, streaming media is intelligently being utilized for social business and e-learning.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

From survey it demonstrated that numerous individuals getting to web are pulled in towards media streaming. This massive interest makes a weight on gathered server ranches at media content supplier, for instance, Video-on-Demand (VoD) suppliers will deal with the required QoS guarantees. The issue ends up being more fundamental with the extending enthusiasm for higher piece rates required for the creating number of better quality video.

Fig 1 Media Streaming

Video delivery frameworks, for example, YouTube, Netflix, Hulu, and so on., have increased extraordinary prevalence on the Internet these days. As per "Cisco Visual Networking Index: Forecast and Methodology". This does exclude video traded through distributed (P2P) record sharing.. Few observations from different person are listed below:

➤ S. Islam, J. Keung, K. Lee, and A. Liu

A forecast technique has been proposed concerning upcoming CPU usage design requests in view of neural systems administration and direct relapse that is of enthusiasm for e-trade applications. However, the majority of the studies foresee the normal streaming limit requests,

few work have likewise concentrated on the unpredictability of the limit request, i.e., the interest change at any point of time in future, which yields more exact danger variables. The forecast of streaming transmission capacity interest is outside the extension.

➤ *Filali, A. S. Hafid, and M. Gendreau*

Applications using Grid computing framework more often than not require assets distribution (e.g., data transmission and CPU) to fulfill their nature of administration (QoS) prerequisites. Given the dynamic way of matrix figuring, QoS backing and adjustment must be a high need to effectively support those applications. A versatile asset provisioning plan is displayed that enhances the data transfer capacity use while fulfilling the required levels of QoS. Boost of data transfer capacity (bandwidth) usage which helps the cloud service suppliers to diminish their costs and expand their incomes.

➤ *Proposed Method*

Today, streaming resource has turned into a component offered by numerous cloud suppliers to substance suppliers with an escalated data transfer capacity request. The streaming of media substance to content viewers situated at various geological locales at ensured information rate is a part of the administration offered by the cloud supplier. The basic method for having so as to execute this administration in the cloud is different server farms inside the systems of the entrance association suppliers (Internet Service Providers) situated at different geological areas. Cloud service provider might need to arrange contracts with various ISPs to co-find their servers into the systems of those ISPs.

In such manner, another gathering of people have centurion contemplating distinctive sorts of agreements among cloud service provider and ISPs for minimizing the costs of cloud suppliers. To the best of the insight, not many studies have explored the issue of improving asset reservation with the goal of reducing the financial expenses for substance suppliers. A decent illustration is exhibited, wherein asset reservation advancement issue is planned to minimize the expenses of substance suppliers, alleged cloud purchasers, utilizing a stochastic programming model. All of the whole of issue plan, unverifiable interest and dubious cloud suppliers' asset costs are considered. Conversely, the advancement issue figured in our work considers a given likelihood appropriation capacity got from previously stated studies for the expectation of media spilling requests. Moreover, the issue of cost minimization is tended to by using the marked down rates offered in the non-direct taxes Equations.

As it observed from related work, we find that the issue of cost minimization for media content suppliers, as far as money related costs by considering the penalties brought about by the over-provisioned or under-provisioned held assets, and the development buy of assets at cloud suppliers for simply the privilege time allotment.

In order to overcome the cost minimization problem, the resources are allocated by using the prediction based allocated implemented by PBRA algorithm and also extending this algorithm with load balancing concept. As many of the people use the android phone in order to make ease of access is done by implemented an android module. The first design stage in which the basic approach for solving the problem is selected is called as System designing. In the system design, the general structure and style are taken. The architecture is the general organization of the system into components called subsystems. The more definite choice which are made in later stages are based on the context of architecture.

The system design gives the abstract representation of data flow, inputs and yields of the system. It additionally portrays the structure, behavior and views of the system. It incorporates a physical design where it explains how data is input into a system, how it is confirmed/validated, how it is prepared, and how it is shown.

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Fig 2 CSP Cloud Service Provider

In this architecture, there are Data owner, Cloud and Web Server and Mobile application. Data owner registers with cloud which in turn cloud allocates certain memory space for that data owner, now data owner can use allocated space for uploading video by logging with the given credentials. With the help of http the cloud uploads video onto the web server. Web server contains the details of how many users have watched the video and other details. Mobile application is used by end-user in order to watch the uploaded video without any delay or disturbance. Cloud server will contain the details of the data owner, available storage space and alerts the data owner with the remaining space.

Dynamic resource allocation algorithm is implemented in cloud as it takes care of allocating the resource using both reservation plan and demand plan.

Prediction-Based Resource Allocation algorithm and load balancing concept:

- *Prediction Based Resource Allocation* (PBRA) that minimizes the monetary expense of asset reservation in the cloud by maximally abusing marked down rates offered in the tariffs, while guaranteeing that adequate assets are saved in the cloud with some level of trust in probabilistic sense. The prediction of CPU use and client access interest for electronic applications has been broadly seen. An versatile asset provisioning plan is

exhibited that improves the data transfer capacity usage while fulfilling the required levels of QoS. In, an enhancement structure for settling on element asset allotment choices under dangerous and dubious working situations was produced to maximize income while decreasing working expenses. The streaming of media content to content viewers situated at various land locales at ensured information rate is a part of the administration offered by the cloud supplier. The normal method for executing this administration in the cloud is by having different server farms inside the systems of the entrance association suppliers (Internet Service Providers, ISPs) situated at proper topographical areas .Cloud administration suppliers may need to arrange contracts with various ISPs to co-find their servers into the systems of those ISPs. In such manner, concentrated on various sorts of agreements between cloud administration suppliers and ISPs with the reason for minimizing the costs of cloud providers. As an outcome an interesting outline methodology is to look at the asset reservation issue from the perspective of content suppliers in minimizing their expenses.

- *Demand Based Android App*
This folder contains the java files for the android application, layout design, string value folder, and also a manifest for android in XML. This folder contains following sub-folders:

- ✓ SRC: This folder contains all the Java Script files where the android user register in server, view videos, submit their opinion.
- ✓ RES: This folder contains the details of the application icon, layout in smart phone, Application name and menu details.
- ✓ LIBS: This folder contains the requierd jar file, android-support-v4

• Demand Based Dynamic Resource Allocation

This folder contains the java files for data owner and server side services. This folder contains following sub-folders

- ✓ SRC: This folder contains all the Java Script files where the data owner requests for space in cloud and other possible user actions.
- ✓ JRE System Library: This folder contains the required jar files, like resources, dsns and so on.

➤ Experimental Results

The expected outcome from this project is to develop a system that allows the data owner to register in cloud and allocate a sufficient memory space to the data owner (Reserved Plan), cloud server should provide a threshold limit for memory space. When the data owner has used enough memory it should allocate the random memory (Demand Plan).

The web server should maintain the list of available videos and load balancing (no. of users increasing on time), view the comments, provides option for admin login.

The end-user must be able to watch the video online without downloading it and without storing it (thus saves both memory and time of downloading it), comment about the watched video.

Fig 3 Shows Screen for Playing Video

Fig 4 Shows Comment Sent Successfully

➤ Interpretation

The performance evaluation is done by comparing the existing resource allocation plan and implemented reservation plan. Existing resource allocation plan in cloud consists of two methods namely; first one fixed reserve time, Second one is demand plan, where in the user dynamically request for resource when they need.

Fig 5 The Graph showing the Resource Cost against Time in Various Methods

III. CONCLUSION

In this anticipate I have concentrated on quality to upgrade and diminishing the primary expense of the system which is passed on. The postulation traverses the ranges of distributed computing, mixed media conveyance, and financial matters. The cloud environment gives flawless base to any utilization. It additionally gives better video

sharing in internet organizing, where the transmissions of video are exceedingly done. This project gives the layout of the streaming and sharing used by various strategies. The idealizing of recordings can be enhanced by utilizing versatile video coding proficiently furthermore by anticipating clients conduct. Also the proposed system can be utilized by the organization when they need to share only set of videos with the authorized users of the organization.

According to the proposed system android user can only watch the video on their smart devices, the future enhancement can be providing the option for uploading the video and also data owner services in the smart devices.

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